

Radio-Based Instruction for Kindergarten: A Parent-Teacher Collaboration Activity in Southville 5A Elementary School Langkiwa, Binan City, Laguna

Charmy M. Hernandez, MAED

Southville 5A Elementary School, Langkiwa, Biñan City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effectiveness of radio-based instruction as a parent-teacher collaboration activity for Kindergarten learners at Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa, Biñan City, Laguna, Philippines, during the School Year 2020-2021. A descriptive research design was employed, involving 228 parents and 13 teachers. Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire and analyzed through frequency, percentage, weighted mean, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r correlation. Findings revealed that the majority of teacher-respondents were young, female, and bachelor's degree holders with several years of teaching experience, while most parent-respondents were female, high school graduates, and not formally employed. Both groups demonstrated a consistently high level of collaboration across all phases of radio-based instruction. Teachers and parents strongly agreed on key practices such as maintaining regular communication, guiding learners during broadcasts, and monitoring task completion after the sessions, as reflected in high mean ratings across indicators. Further analysis indicated that differences and relationships between respondents' demographic characteristics and their level of collaboration were not statistically significant, suggesting that effective collaboration is not influenced by profile variables but rather by shared responsibility and engagement. Based on these findings, a Mother Tongue-based radio instructional script was developed to support early literacy. The study concludes that radio-based instruction, strengthened by active parent-teacher collaboration, is a viable and effective supplemental learning modality in alternative education settings.

KEYWORDS: *Radio-based instruction; parent-teacher collaboration; kindergarten education; mother tongue instruction; early literacy; distance learning; audio-based learning, Laguna, Philippines.*

1. THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

The new normal has a great impact on our educational system that causes pupils to stay-at-home. This makes it even more challenging for students to study better due to no face-to-face instruction. Teaching, monitoring pupils' progress and learning will become more difficult during the pandemic to return to a path of faster learning improvement.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education released DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020, the adoption of Basic Continuity Plan in light of the COVID-19

Public Health emergency which mandates the public and private institutions to use multiple learning modalities and platforms that schools may employ in the absence of face-to-face instruction. One of the platforms is the Radio-based Instruction.

Based on DM-CI-2020-0016-2, the Suggested strategies in implementing Distance learning Delivery modalities (DLDM) for School year 2020-2021, Radio-based Instruction shall be implemented in areas with access in Radio stations with a program

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dedicated to deliver the Radio-based lessons. The self-learning modules are converted into radio-instruction and aligned to MELCS. The duration of the lessons shall depend on the length of modules beaded on the target competencies to the allowable airtime agreed upon the radio stations. Further clarifications regarding the lessons shall be done by the learning facilitator or teacher through phone calls, chat, text messaging, among others and guidance from parents/guardians are strictly required while listening to audio lessons.

In compliance with the DMCI, the Division of Biñan adopted Project SOAR (Strengthen On-Air lessons in Reading) to strengthen the Radio-based instruction as a supplemental learning modality. Since the local government of Biñan has its own Radio station, the Division of Biñan requested the City Mayor through a formal letter to air the lessons in *Radyo Biñan* 87.9 FM to reach the student for continuous learning. The approved timeslot is 10:00 to 11:00 in the morning from Monday to Friday. The objectives of this project are; to improve the reading and comprehension skills of all Kinder in Mother-tongue, Grade 1 to 3 for English and Filipino; nurture a culture collaboration with the schools, communities and different stakeholders through the project and serve as a supplementary source of learning to students under modular distance learning modality.

The Division Memo No. 196, s. 2020, entitled Teaching Loads and Assignments of teachers handling RBI as Supplemental Learning Modality supports the utilization of Radio-Based Instruction and gives 1 hour teaching load deduction to the teacher broadcaster and technical team to prepare and edit scripts, practice broadcasting, recording, and editing audio lessons. The audio lessons output is dedicated to deliver the Radio-based instruction.

As the Radio Instruction launched, the School Memo No. 007, s. 2020, entitled Broadcasting of Radio-Based Instruction was released. The school head of Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa announced the implementation of RBI as supplementary modality in reading specifically, Mother-Tongue for Kindergarten and English and Filipino subjects for Grade 1 to Grade 3 pupils for the school year 2020- 2021 which will be guided by Readiness Skill Textbook and Self-Learning Modules. Pupils are encouraged to listen to the audio lessons 45 minutes a week to complete their weekly learning tasks. The program focuses on five components: phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. Kindergarten reading programs concentrate on phonemic awareness and phonics.

To monitor the participation of the parents and learners, the following task are designed: Before the broadcast, parents and guardian are advised to prepare the Self learning modules or Workbook and recall the last week lesson to their child. Teachers should constantly remind the parent/ guardian regarding the schedule of broadcast via various platforms like text messaging and sending messages to group chats. During the broadcast, parents are advised to guide their child while performing the task given by the radio teacher and they may send their answers through Facebook comment in *Radyo* Biñan 87.9 page while teachers document the participation of their learners. After the broadcast, the parents and guardians are advised to help the learners to complete the weekly task and submit the output on the schedule day of retrieval and give feedback to the teachers for the questions while teachers are advised to follow up the learners for clarification and areas of confusion encountered by the learners about the audio lessons.

Background of the Study

The study aimed to determine the collaboration of parent and teacher in Radio- based instruction as its first year of Distance learning. Southville 5A Elementary School is in the Modular Distance learning modality. It is located in the *Pabahay* Program or relocation site at Brgy. Langkiwa Biñan City. It is where families of 4262 pupils were relocated coming from different provinces and cities. Radio is available to them and basic among the other gadgets to be used for their education.

The Radio-based instruction in kindergarten as a supplemental learning modality in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa familiarizes learners with letter- sound in the Mother-Tongue subject for the school year 2020-2021. Mother Tongue for Kinder focused only on phonological awareness, and alphabet knowledge. The coverage of the radio lessons for the first quarter are the letter-sound of Mm, Aa, Tt, Nn, Ee, Ng, Ññ, and Ss. Second quarter letter-sounds are Bb, Ii, Cc, Jj, Pp, Qq, Ff and Gg. In the third quarter, the letters are Uu, Rr, Dd, Oo, Ll, Hh, and Kk. Lastly, for the fourth quarter letter-sounds are Vv, Ww, Xx, Yy and Zz.

Phonological awareness is one of the most important skills a child must demonstrate in kindergarten. Understanding of letter sounds by identifying/picking out the letter of the distinct initial sounds in words, match sounds with letters, and hear specific letter sounds by listening to a story and singing a song. Alphabet knowledge skill identifies letter names and sounds (Standards and Competencies for Five-Year-Old Filipino Children, 2016). The learner identifies the letter in the alphabet, giving the sound of each

letter using the provided workbooks and worksheets, the learners trace, copy and write different strokes through audio lessons making the child practice its handwriting with the help of their parents or guardian. The learners practice tracing letters simultaneously with the instruction of a radio teacher.

Teachers are advised to remind the parents or guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast via various platforms. Advisers are instructed to check pupils' attendance during the broadcast and document the participation of learners and parents or guardians through narrative reports, follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion encountered by pupils about the audio lessons through phone calls, chat, text messages and others. Parents or guardians are encouraged to assist their children by preparing the materials the learner needs while tuning in to the audio lesson, guide learners in completing the learning tasks or activity sheets after listening to the audio lessons. Parents also need to give feedback about the questions of the learners regarding the audio lessons and submit the learning outputs of the learners during the schedule of retrieval.

Therefore, the researcher chose to determine the parent-teacher collaboration activities in Radio-based Instruction in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa.

Statement of the Problem

The main thrust of the study is to determine the Radio-based instruction for Kindergarten: A Parent-Teacher Collaboration Activity in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa, Biñan City, Laguna.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Teacher
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 - 1.1.3. Educational Attainment
 - 1.1.4. Length of Service
 - 1.2. Parent
 - 1.2.1. Age
 - 1.2.2. Sex
 - 1.2.3. Educational Attainment
 - 1.2.4. Employment Status
2. How do parents and teachers collaborate in radio-based instruction in terms of?
 - 2.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 2.2. During the Broadcast
 - 2.3. After the Broadcast
3. What radio-based instruction Script in Mother-Tongue for Kindergarten may be developed?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was stated as follows:

1. There is no significant difference on how parents' and teachers' collaboration in Radio-Based Instruction in terms of:
 - 1.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 1.2. During the Broadcast
 - 1.3. After the Broadcast
2. There is no significant relationship between respondents' profile and how they collaborate in Radio-Based Instruction in terms of:
 - 2.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 2.2. During the Broadcast
 - 2.3. After the Broadcast

Significance of the Study

This study was conducted to determine the parent-teacher collaboration activity and success of Radio-based instruction for kindergarten.

The findings of this study were found significantly to the following:

To the **Local Government Unit**, the result of this study will serve as the basis to help and seek the needs of the community to continue the education with the help of radio instruction.

To the **School Administrators**, the result of this study will serve as a valuable basis in making plans to help learners understand the lesson very well, communicate with the parents and know the problems encountered at home so that the school can plan to solve the problem since it is the first year of implementation.

To the **Teachers**, the findings of the study will serve as a concrete basis for them to generate strategies in reading using audio instruction suited to the needs of the pupils. It will help to plan, design, and implement various strategies in teaching reading to improve instruction for the new normal with the help of their parents. This study will show the procedures that are not given much attention by the teacher.

To the **Parents**, the study will show what is least done in collaboration with teachers in radio-based instruction. The radio lesson will make it easier for their child to learn as it is the basics of those modalities.

To the **Pupils**, the result of the study will serve as a valuable basis in determining the collaboration activity of parent-teachers for radio-based instruction. In addition, the result will become instrumental in organizing and managing activities for various types of learners in radio instruction for the new normal situations.

To the **Future Researchers**, the finding will hopefully provide information that will be useful to the next or future researcher who aims to conduct the same study.

Scope and Limitations

The study was conducted to determine the parent-teacher collaboration activity in Radio-based Instruction at Southville 5A Elementary School, Brgy. Langkiwa Biñan City during the School Year 2020-2021 in terms of before, during and after the broadcast. It covered the broadcast of Mother Tongue audio lessons among kindergarten pupils where the researcher is the key facilitator in radio-based instruction.

It involved 228 parents of kindergarten out of a total 533. Likewise, the teachers will be included in the study composed of 13 teachers from Kinder. They are the subject of the study because they have direct experience in the actual broadcast of Radio-based instruction, while the learners are listening to the audio lessons.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined within the context of the study.

Actual time. It indicates the time started and time ended in the whole actual programs.

After the broadcast. It denotes the collaboration done by parents and teachers after the broadcast. It refers to guiding the learners in accomplishing the task by referring to the home learning plan, clarifying the instructions and giving follow up to the teachers for the areas of confusion encountered by learners and submitting the output in the scheduled retrieval.

Before the broadcast. It refers to the activities that parents-teachers perform in preparation for the broadcast of audio lessons such as preparing the weekly schedule of broadcast, reminding through text, chat messages, informing the platform you access in broadcast. It also includes the preparation of learners' material before the broadcast and guiding the learners to review or recall the last week's lesson.

Collaboration. It is an activity of parent and teacher partnership working on a common task more effectively in academic progress of the students before, during and after the broadcast and to achieve its one goal.

During the broadcast. It refers to the activities done by parents and teachers while tuned-in in the broadcast. It covered the checking of attendance in any of the following forms such as informing the teachers by sending pictures, informing the teacher or sending messages while the child is tuned in and

assisting and instructing the learners to perform the task given by the radio-teacher.

Guest Teacher. A Kindergarten teacher who is invited to deliver and present his/her own radio-script lesson for the day via radio-based instruction.

Program ID. A song sung by Marco Sison. It is a signal that the radio-based instruction will be aired soon. The links are sent to the parents and learners during this time.

Radio-Based Instruction. The delivery of self-learning modules converted into audio lessons broadcasted through a local radio frequency. In the study, it refers to a supplementary learning modality in reading literacy for Kinder to Grade 3 using audio lessons transmitted via *Radyo Biñan* 87.9 FM.

Radio Broadcasting. The transmission of audio lesson using radio. The local channel is the *Radyo Biñan*, a government-owned radio station, used to transmit the lessons in the areas covered in the locality.

Radio Broadcast Structure. It is the content of the 45-minute program and composed of program Id, introduction and song, greetings, *kumustahan* and Introducing of the guest teacher by the hosts, review of the previous lesson, Introduction of lesson, motivation or development, lesson proper and engagement, recap of the lesson, assimilation and assignment, reminders, and goodbyes.

Running time. It is the time or minutes allotted per content in the lessons in radio instruction.

Supplemental Learning Modality. It is an additional mode of instruction delivered using a radio. In the study, it refers to Reading Literacy for Kinder through broadcasted audio lessons via *Radyo Biñan* 87.9 FM.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents and discusses literature and studies that provide more insights into the nature of the present study and its theoretical framework as well.

Radio-Based Instruction

Radio is a basic technology that can be used to support education, especially in the new normal situation. According to Khan (2015) the accessibility of radio in the developing countries of the world is evident and through radio, teachers can teach practical skills.

According to Ullah & Khan (2017) radio plays a vital part in communicating, entertaining, and informing daily life to access effectively to the broader

audiences in urban and rural areas. In addition, Agbaje, et al. (2017) stressed that radio as used in live broadcasting is one of the technological tools and resources used to transfer information to enhance the educational system. Similarly, Elliot & Lashley (2017) emphasized that radio instruction is a distance education system that combines radio broadcasts with active learning to improve educational quality and teaching practices. The study of Ignatiew (2017) revealed that radio invites the listener to recreate the minds of the listeners with images that are not conveyed and limitless to the listeners imagination. In doing the radio instruction, Jacob & Ensign (2020) suggested doing something exceptional can preserve the attention span of the children for 40-45 minutes in which the radio broadcasting in Biñan aired every Friday from 10:00 to 11:00 am with 45 mins interaction and 15 minutes for question and answer via Facebook live. Meanwhile, the 'Broad Class – Listen to Learn' program (Hundred, 2020) concluded that the program's evaluation using radio instruction showed a significant effect on the children's holistic growth, attendance, and performance.

Nonetheless, Radio broadcasting is one of the tools or platforms that needs guidance and presence of parents because the children's attention span was unusually low and after ten minutes, children lost their interest and got bored, either left or stopped listening completely.

The Radio-based instruction content is focused on reading practices. Since kindergarten is the foundational stage, reading needs an excellent phonics instruction for children to be able to use them and retain them throughout their lives. Gentry (2017) discovered one of the five best practices in teaching kindergarten. Teaching one letter a week by listening attentively and singing the letter to break the code. (Light & McNaughton, 2019) suggest starting by teaching the sounds of the letters, not their names. Knowing the names of letters is not necessary to read or write. Knowledge of letter names can interfere with successful decoding. In fact, according to (Duke & Mesmer, 2018) Naming letter is only one element of letter comprehension. It is the use of letter-sound material that advances the reading and spelling of children.

Common cause of phonics instruction failure are inadequate review or repetition cycle, lack of application to real writing and reading experiences, inappropriate reading materials, inappropriate pacing of lessons, no comprehensive or mastery assessment tools, transitioning to multisyllabic is too late and overemphasize phonics. In these findings, the study of (Rogowsky, Calhoun, & Tallal, 2016) showed that

the using different modality in comprehension did not matter even if learners listen to an audiobook or read from a book or both listen and read simultaneously because learners received an equal amount of information. (Yildirim & Yildirim, 2016) Listening plays an important role both in everyday life and in academic settings. Young-Suk & Pilcher, (2016) defined listening comprehension as the ability to understand spoken language in conversations, stories, and informational oral texts that involve the processes of obtaining and forming meaning. They found out in a follow-up study in Korean Grade 1 children that an inferencing skill and theory of mind made independent contributions. Language instruction should be established throughout the school day, exploiting teachable moments. Also, the study of Labarrete (2019) concluded that augmenting means contextualizing the content by using texts that are common to them and concentrating the skills that need to be learned. (Ivone & Renandya, 2019) Comprehensive and interesting extensive listening resources inspire learners to keep listening to the target language.

Each interaction with a child promotes the development needed for academic and social success. Many people believe that the interaction does not officially begin until the child enters the school. (Anderson & Rodriguez, 2019) Parent's involvement in children's literacy has an impact in the development of the learner.

The study of (Jose, et al., 2020) showed that increased participation in shared parent-child interactions could be a significant goal in deliberate attempts to increase early reading achievement. Reading through a radio instruction is newly implemented in Biñan City. Bell et al. (2020) defines radio lack interactivity, parents and guardians can overcome this shortcoming by interacting with their children and accompanied with printed materials. In the same way, the radio-teacher should be prepared enough to face these gaps and for the new normal. The study of (Jung, 2016) discovered the relationships between parental beliefs about school readiness, family engagement in home learning activities, and children's reading achievement in kindergarten. (Hands, 2015) School and Community collaboration is important to meet the needs of society and create links to meet one goal. (Epstein, 2018) defined the Partnership as involvement, participation, collaboration to improve schools and maximize success of all learners.

According to the study of Islam (2017) conducted an experiment involving regular, face to face meeting in Bangladesh in which regular parent-teacher meeting suggested parents to spend more time with their

children and monitor the schoolwork. In addition, the study of Lara & Saracostti (2019) shows that parental and teacher collaboration can support learning activities at home through communication between family and school. Aside from improvement of test scores of the pupils, the students' attitudes and behavior towards studying was also improved. Findings suggest that higher engagement in shared parent-child activities may be an important focus in intentional efforts aimed at enhancing early reading achievement.

More mother-parents are interacting with teachers than father-parents. partnership. In the study of Mora-Ruano, et al (2018) women collaborate more than men when they are the same gender in two or three forms of collaboration such as synchronization, co-construction, and interest. Nonetheless, when parents and teachers work together, they form a partnership that is vital not only in school and family but also the child. (Lau & Power, 2018) (Lau & Ng, 2019).

Pepito (2019) emphasized to have a collaborative teacher-parent partnership, specific roles of both parents and teachers must be clarified first. Ahmadi (2016) Myende & Nhlumayo (2020) suggest that when cooperating with schools, parents should examine the relevant concepts of parental involvement and evaluate the roles of parents from various scenarios.

The role of teachers are organizer, controller, evaluator, resource, tutor, and prompter, help the learners and provide guidance in radio instruction, develop the ideas towards the lesson and encourage learners in every stage while listening in broadcast. These activities are possible when parents or guardians of the learners are around while listening into the radio-based instruction. Parents and teachers should practice involvement such as Learning at home and collaborating with the community Pepito (2019). Firmanto, Sumarsono & Nur (2020) Parents serve as tutors for their children at home under this learning paradigm, while the school produces learning materials with comprehensive methods and an organized schedule.

Learning at home emphasized providing parents with the required information on some effective ways and techniques of guiding children in their learning at home. Teachers may narrate the procedures in guiding the learners in radio instruction. Parents have a desire to be involved in their children's education but lack the required information on how to do so. Collaborating with the community emphasized the practice of volunteering. It means that parents help and support the school programs and projects for the enhancement and success of current practices.

According to Pact (2016) Monitoring is the practice of gathering and reviewing information systematically to monitor the success of the curriculum in meeting objectives and observe improvements in conflict or surroundings. With the help of parents, school programs and projects will be achieved.

The conduct of Radio-based instruction in the locale of the study is guided by a school issuance articulating the specific roles of the parents, teachers, and learners before, during and after the broadcast of audio lessons.

Before the Broadcast

Equally important in the radio-based instruction in the setting of the study is the roles of parents since they are the immediate adults in place of the teachers while learners learn at home. Teachers are expected to provide the parents/guardians a copy of the weekly schedule. Bhamani, et al. (2020) Implementing a schedule helps children feel less restless and more productive. A schedule routine helps children to understand the importance of time, scheduling and doing assignments on a given timeline and helps them shape their future work habits.

Sending to the parents the link of broadcast is one of the areas that makes the parents and teachers collaborate. Parent and teacher collaboration may involve different ways via direct communication such as text message, chat messages, phone call, home visitation or email. The teachers are expected to constantly remind the parents/guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast. The parents acknowledge the reminder of the teacher in the schedule of broadcast. Bordalba & Bochaca (2019) findings revealed that parents and teachers display more positive stances on the use of digital media like Facebook where the management team promotes the use of emails or online platforms for family-school communication.

Through orientations, the parents are aware that before the broadcast they are to prepare/ready the materials of learners needed while listening to the audio lessons. Learners prepare their self-learning module or workbook and recall the previous lesson. (Tety, 2016) findings revealed that teachers consider instructional materials as key to academic performance. Without textbooks, activity sheets or other learning materials learning is not possible for preschool learners.

According to Solak (2016) Pre-task exercises in listening through audio lessons are focused on arousing interest before the main action among students. (International Literacy Association, 2019) A

Systematic teaching involves a review and repetition to achieve mastery and makes the new experience more apparent and easier to understand for students. (EnglishPost.org, 2021) Pre-Listening Activities prepare students by making them involved in the subject and the next level while listening which the students will illustrate their comprehension of what is being heard. Parents may give a set of questions to their child before the broadcast of the lesson to ensure that the child is attentively listening to the last week's lesson. In doing this activity, learners will practice thinking about what was discussed in the previous lesson.

During the Broadcast

During the broadcast, teachers check the attendance of the pupils by phone calls and text messages. (Yuvaraj, et al, 2017) conclude that attendance is an important matter since it is one of the primary ways to check the regularity of every student. Even though teachers cannot monitor the parents in their task, encouraging parents to send messages in Facebook live, sending messages or pictures to the teachers on Radio based instruction will do.

The parents assist their children while tuned in to the audio lesson. The kindergarten learners are guided by the teachers and parents/guardians in the radio-based instruction. Anora (2020) defined listening requires clear instructions and explanations in each activity for students to get a perfect understanding. The lesson starts with an Alphabasa and becomes part of the weekly routine to familiarize the learners with the alphabet and its sound. (Neuman, 2020) The alphabetic principle is one of the more important skills for children to develop using lots of experiences. Children must listen to the sound everyday making the lesson short and enjoyable by incorporating activities and games.

In the lesson proper, the radio teacher engages the learners by repeating the sound of the letters. (Berrill, 2021) defines phonics as a reading approach that involves the connection of sounds to written letters and involves foreign words "sounding out." Repeating the letters and sounds, building strong communication lines with parents or guardians, incorporating art into learning letters and sounds and singing and dancing to songs (Education to the Core, 2016). Aranas (2016) found out that teachers can customize lessons with interesting learning materials, engage students during instruction, and encourage them to repeat the lessons for independent practice on their own. Similarly, Ose (2016) found out that by providing different sensory experiences, teachers can help their students learn and retain information.

Radio teacher encouraged the listeners to open their textbook as reference for the lesson. They give the name of the reference material and page number as a guide. The findings of the study (Wolf, 2015) showed that exposing children to print-to-sound activities learned to decode CVC words more easily than children who received letter name instruction alone did not improve their reading ability. Ivone & Renandya (2019) findings that using authentic materials can be made more comprehensible, giving learners the chance to read accompanied by written text while listening. (Rahman, et al. 2019) findings in their study that in order to provide parents with ideas about children's learning activities, it is important to provide them the opportunity to observe activities. While the learners are listening to the lesson and using the reference material, parents do their task to observe the child. (Duke & Mesmer, 2018) Children need to practice pointing to words themselves. A great way to do this is to allow children to point to words in a line of print. (Yildirim & Yildirim, 2016) If a person listens, replies, and asks/answers questions, it is active listening. Mullis, Martin, & Sainsbury, (2016) Readers can create meaning from text in a variety of forms. In the same way, Juwariyah, Slamer & Kustiono (2019) conclude that parents should allow their children to express what they see and feel so that they can simply react to what they are given. During the broadcast, they are expected to perform the task given by the radio teacher through the guidance of the parents. Their active participation during the broadcast is monitored by the teacher.

Using games in radio lessons provides an active participation of the learners. Ngamkiatkhajorn & Kanoksilapatham, (2018) found out that early literacy skills are considered a fundamental key to elevate a learner's language abilities. Arnsten (n.d.) students loved playing a game or completing a specific activity for a topic when it was first taught. Using games and tasks related to the content that has been taught, it would allow the participants to practice more and understand better.

After the Broadcast

After the broadcast, the parents' guide their children in accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets; give feedback to teachers about questions and clarifications about the audio lessons; and submit learning outputs during scheduled retrieval.

The learners are tasked to complete/accomplish the activity sheets for the week. According to Sønsthagen (2020) in this time of pandemic and parents are the one who can monitor the learners, parents should share information regarding students' daily routine.

Baralt & Gomez (2017) says that implementing task-based methodology during real-time is fundamentally different from face-to-face interaction.

Parents share feedback to the teachers regarding the areas of confusion in radio lessons and/or observed progress with their child during the radio instruction. (Kraft 2017) proved that messaging has also proved to be effective in boosting parent engagement and student achievement. According to Halimah & Andriyadi (2018) through a short message service (SMS)-gateway will help parents to gather information from Kindergarten teachers. Kuhn et. al. (2016) parents and teachers of young children must create successful partnerships. Waterford (2018) parents and teachers should pay attention to one another and exchange ideas or inquiries. (Al- Batal, n.d.) describes that a post-listening practice is a follow-up to the listening activity which attempts to use the skills acquired by listening to improve other skills, such as speaking or writing. Parents may ask some questions to their child regarding the lesson that was tackled.

In addition, Kuhn et. al., (2016) encourages parents to keep track of their children's progress and track their progress toward their goals. Parents and teachers discuss the necessary adjustments in interactions and/or learning opportunities using data observed and as needed, adjust to new developmental demands and learning opportunities as early as possible.

During retrieval, parents send to the school the output of their child for the whole week. Knauf (2020) suggests that the teachers created techniques primarily to gain time for documentation and to organize it in such a way that they can cope with the additional responsibilities it implies. Teachers documented all the output of the learners in an

envelope to ensure the documents of the learners and output are intact. However, Higgins & Cherrington (2017) highlighted the significance of making learning visible by accomplishing the tasks, rather than simply providing photographic evidence (DepEd Order 007, 2020) defined the parent-teacher conference as an opportunity to bring parents and teachers together in cooperation, to encourage academic performance and fulfillment for learners. In addition, the teacher will address the academic and social progress of pupils to the parents, the behavior of their children and the performance of the learners. Parent-teacher conferences, phone conversations, and committee meetings are all examples of two-way communication which will give opportunities for parents and teachers to interact with one another.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 shows the research paradigm. The researcher will use the input- process-output framework.

The inputs of the study are the variables that the researcher wanted to measure and gather which includes the respondents' profile of teachers in terms of age, gender, educational attainment and length of service, parent's age, gender, occupation, and educational attainment. Also, part of the inputs are the ways how parents and teachers collaborate in radio-based instruction before, during and after the broadcast.

The second frame is the process or procedure of the researcher to gather information which is the survey questionnaire.

The last frame is the outcome which will grant vital information needed in the enhancement of audio lessons. The Radio-based Instruction script in Mother Tongue with parent-teacher collaboration will be the outcome of the study.

Figure 1: Paradigm of the study

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the explanations of the methods and techniques used in gathering data, the sampling procedure, instrumentation, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The descriptive survey design was utilized in determining the parent-teacher collaboration activity for radio-based instruction for kindergarten in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa.

According to Boudah (2019), the descriptive research design provides a picture of a condition or phenomena in which the researcher describes the respondents' perception from the responses in a survey or interview questions. The design is the most appropriate since this study deals with describing data to come up with factual results.

Participants of the Study

The respondents were composed of parents and teachers from Kindergarten of Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa. The respondents consist of 228 parents in Kinder and 13 teachers in Kindergarten teaching Mother-tongue.

Instrumentation

The instrument used to get the answer in this study was the researcher-made survey form through a printed material. It was composed of several parts. The first part of the questionnaire was the data privacy agreement under the provision of the RA10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the researcher states the purpose of the study and all the personal information and responses given by the respondents were treated confidentially and secured properly and used for this research only. The second part was the demographic profile of the respondents. The teacher's age, gender, educational attainment, and length of service were needed for the study; while the age, gender, occupation, and educational attainment were needed for the parents. The third part aimed to determine the participation of the respondents in the radio-based instruction. To quantify the responses, a 4-point Likert Scale is used with corresponding verbal descriptions, namely: 4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 - Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree.

The instrument was subjected to a dry-run for validation purposes, among 10 parents and 10

teachers who are not involved in the study. The results of the dry-run used in revising and improving the instrument before its actual administration.

The researcher administered the survey questionnaire in printed format to the parents and teachers. The survey questionnaire was distributed and retrieved during the distribution/retrieval of self-learning modules. The proper health care protocol and ensure that there will be social distancing were observed. Finally, the accomplished survey questionnaire was collected, and the responses tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering phase commenced with the researcher sending a request letter seeking permission to conduct the study to the school head. Upon approval, the researcher produced the actual number of questionnaires for parents and teachers. These were distributed during the distribution/retrieval of self-learning modules. Both respondents were given ample time to accomplish the instrument. The questionnaires were retrieved, and the responses were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to derive salient findings from the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After administering the questionnaire, all the data were summarized in tabular form and subjected to statistical analysis using the following formulae:

- 1. Frequency and percentage distribution** was used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents.

$$\% = F/N \times 100$$

Where:

% = Percentage Distribution

F = Frequency Distribution

N = total number of respondent

- 2. Weighted Mean** was used to determine the parent-teacher collaboration on radio-based instruction.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Where:

X = weighted mean

$\sum fx$ = sum of the product of all frequencies and weights

n = number of samples

- 3. One-Way ANOVA** was used to test the significant difference of parent-teacher collaboration in radio-based instruction during, before and after broadcast.

$$MS_b = \frac{SS_b}{K-1}$$

MS_b = Mean Squares between groups

SS_b = Sum of Squares between groups

N = Number of cases combined across all groups

K = Number of groups

- 4. Pearson r Coefficient of Correlation** was used to determine the significant relationship between the respondent's profile and how they collaborate in the radio-based instruction.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Where,

r = Pearson Correlation Coefficient

x_i = x variable samples

y_i = y variable sample

\bar{x} = mean of values in x variable

\bar{y} = mean of values in y variable

4. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter contains the presentation and analysis of the data gathered relative to the specific questions asked in the study.

The first part presents the profile of the participants according to demographic variables. The second part deals with mean scores of Parents and Teachers Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of before, during and after broadcast.

PART I Respondents Demographic Profile

Teacher. The table 1 shows the demographic profile of teachers as participants in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service. As for age, in the group of 21-30 years old there are 8 or 61.54% and in the group of 31-40 years old are 5 or 38.46%. The teachers in the locale of the study belong to the early adults. They are characterized by energy, enthusiasm, and dedication to their work as teachers of the Radio-based Instruction. **Gula-gula (2021)** noted teachers between 21-30 and 31-40 were young teachers who are energetic and display enthusiasm towards teaching. Data also disclosed that the teachers are relatively mature in terms of age and can provide sufficient information on their collaboration with the radio-based instruction.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Teacher Participants

Characteristics	F	%
Age		
21-30	8	61.54
31-40	5	38.46
Total	13	100
Sex		
Male	0	0
Female	13	100
Total	13	100
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor degree	8	61.54
Bachelors with MA Units	5	38.46
Total	13	100
Length of Service		
3 years and below	4	30.77
4-9 years	8	61.54
10-14 years	1	7.69
Total	13	100

Relative to the sex, 13 or 100% of teachers are female. The sex variable is assumed to influence the collaboration of teachers and parents in radio broadcasting. The teaching force in the locale of the study is composed of female teachers. Wong (2019) reported the dominance of female teachers in the pre-elementary years which was attributed to their child-rearing responsibilities and motherly instincts. Nalubega (2015) explained that women are traditionally perceived as mothers and children nurturers, which makes people think they are more suitable for primary education than men. Women teachers are expected to be loving and caring, which are qualities demanded by young learners. Furthermore, early education requires a lot of patience and tolerance which are natural endowment of women.

In the educational attainment of the respondents, 8 or 61.54% teachers are Bachelor's degree which means that they are qualified in teaching profession while 5 out of 13 teachers or 38.46% are Bachelors with MA units who pursue to continue their profession. The teachers in the locale of the study were all qualified as Kindergarten teachers. Majority of them showed basic entry requirements as Kindergarten teachers. There were also a few who have acquired units in the master's program which indicates that they are concerned with their educational and professional development. The educational qualification of teachers affects their collaboration in radio-based instruction. According to Manning et. al. (2017) a positive association exists between teacher

qualification and the quality of early childhood education. Mandating qualified teachers lead to a significant improvement for both process and structural quality of early childhood education. The present study shares similar findings to that of Manning et. al. (2017) indicating that teacher qualification showed a positive and significant statistical relationship with program structure, program activities, interaction, and personal care. These areas are deemed to be the collaboration of teachers in the implementation of the radio-based instruction.

As per length of service, the majority of the teachers are 4-9 years with 8 or 61.54%. Followed by 3 years and below with 4 or 30.77% and 1 or 7.69% in the group of 10-14 years in service. Most of the teachers showed less than 10 years in the service because the school is newly built that is why the teachers are newly hired. It means that the Kindergarten teachers in the locale of the study were novice teachers. According to Mohan (2016) novice teachers need at least 3 years to achieve competence and several more to reach proficiency. The present study assumes that the number of years spent by teachers in teaching gives them more experience and opportunities to enhance their pedagogical skills. On the contrary, since the radio-based instruction is a new strategy for teaching reading in Kindergarten, the teachers have limited experience in its implementation.

Parents. Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the parents' participants.

Majority of the parents are in the age bracket of 21-30 years old with 99 or 43.42% comprising almost half of the total population. Followed by 31-40 years old with 97 out of 228 participants and the least of the age bracket is 41-50 years old with 32 or 14.04%. The parents of the Kindergarten pupils belonged to the early adult stage. It is assumed that the age characteristics of the parents influence their collaboration in the radio-based instruction. Catalini (2020) stated age at parenthood affects the educational achievement of children, mostly of low-and-middle educated parents. Lee and Lustik (2021) stated that good parents possess common traits across ages. They naturally want their kids to succeed, hence they provide guidance and support to their child. They know that it is important for their kids to do things for themselves; therefore, they allow their child to do things on their own, whether it is homework or chores. The idea concurs with the study about the collaboration of parents with the radio-based instruction.

Table 2 Demographic Profile of Parent Participants

Characteristics	F	%
Age		
20 and below		
21-30	99	43.42
31-40	97	42.54
41-50	32	14.04
51 and above		
Total	228	100
Sex		
Male	43	18.86
Female	185	81.14
Total	228	100
Educational Attainment		
Elementary graduate	24	10.53
High School graduate	165	72.37
College undergraduate	32	14.04
Bachelor's degree	7	3.07
Total	228	100
Employment Status		
Employed	65	28.51
Unemployed	163	71.49
Total	228	100

As to the parents' sex, 43 or 18.86% male and 185 or 81.14% are female. Majority of the parents who participated in the study were females corresponding to the mothers available at home to assist their child in the broadcast of radio-based instruction. It indicates that the mothers are involved in the learning of the kindergarten pupils. Lau & Power (2018) determined maternal involvement in kindergarten. The results showed that mothers' involvement in language and cognitive activities during kindergarten predicted better school adjustment. On the contrary, the study Al Khatib (2020) showed that there was a statistically significant association between parent gender and involvement in early childhood education.

When it comes to the educational attainment of the respondents, the majority of the parents are Highschool graduates with 165 or 72.37%, College undergraduates with 32 or 14.04%, Elementary graduates 24 or 10.53% and Bachelor's degree with 7 or 3.07%. Majority of the parents were high school graduates, indicating they have completed basic education. It is assumed that the level of education of parents influences the achievement of children in radio-based instruction. Parents with higher levels of education have higher rates of involvement in their children's schools. Parents with Bachelor degree recorded higher attendance in a school or class activity compared with parents having less than high school education. (Child Trends, 2018) Parents' educational attainment is associated with the quality

of children's educational experiences and their academic achievement whether they are in public school, in private school or being homeschooled. (The Conditions of Education, 2016) Lau & Power (2018) mother education was positively associated with children's cognitive skills. Moreover, mother's involvement predicts the amount of time they spend with their children. Mothers who engaged in more cognitive language at home tended to have children who showed better school adjustment over time. Before the children enter primary school, the more mothers engage in language and cognitive skills at home and communicate with the teachers, the more adjusted are the children in school. However, Al Khatib (2020) revealed in his study that parents' educational level was not significantly associated with parent involvement.

Relative to employment status, the majority of the parents are unemployed with 163 or 71.49% and 65 or 28.51% are employed parents. In this regard, it can be seen that most parents are focused on their child. They regularly supervise their child during the radio-based instruction broadcast and monitor their child's work. According to Anderson & Rodriguez, (2019) parents' involvement in children's literacy has an impact in the development of the learner. Horisch (2016) explained that maternal and paternal employment affect children's cognitive and educational attainment. On the one hand, children may benefit from higher levels of family income, on the other hand, parental employment reduces the amount of time parents spend with their children. Parents of students living in households with income at or above minimum rate have higher rates of involvement than those below minimum wage rates. Low-income workers tend to have rigid work schedules, which can make it difficult for them to participate in their children's school activities. Household poverty status is associated with the quality of children's educational experiences and their academic achievement whether they are in public school, in private school or being homeschooled. (The Conditions of Education, 2016).

Part II. Mean Scores on the Parents and Teachers Collaboration on Radio-based Instruction

Table 3 shows the teachers' collaboration on radio-based instruction before the broadcast with a grand mean of 3.44 with verbal interpretation strongly agree.

Indicator 1 "Give a weekly schedule of the broadcast." Indicator 1.1 Provides the parents a printed copy of the weekly schedule of broadcast with rated mean of 3.08 and verbal interpretation Agree; Indicator 1.2 Informs the parents of the coverage or

topic of the audio lesson personally during retrieval with rated mean of 3.38 with Strongly agree as interpretation; and in the Indicator 1.3 Sends the link of the broadcast through Facebook chat with 3.54 weighted mean and verbal interpretation strongly agree. Teachers obtain the highest indicator 1.3 which means teachers send to the parents 5 mins before the broadcast through chat or Facebook group messenger. Data disclosed that teachers inform the parents about the coverage / topic of the lesson because most of the time a relative or family member is the representative

in school and does not relay the information to the parents. It indicates that teachers give a printed copy of the weekly schedule of broadcast to the parents because not all parents have their own cellular phone to receive a message from the teacher and weekly schedule is announced during the orientation in the 1st quarter and 2nd quarter. (Bhamani, et al. 2020) Implementing a schedule helps children feel less restless and more productive. Sending to the parents the link of broadcast is one of the areas that makes the parents and teachers collaborate.

Table 3 Mean Score of Teachers' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Before Broadcast

Indicator	Teacher	
	WM	Intp.
1. Give weekly schedule of the broadcast		
1.1 Provides the parents a printed copy of the weekly schedule of broadcast	3.08	A
1.2 Informs the parents of the coverage or topic of the audio lesson personally during retrieval	3.38	SA
1.3 Sends the link of the broadcast through Facebook chat	3.54	SA
2. Constantly remind the parents/guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast		
2.1 Sends a text or chat message to the parents		
2.2 Call the parents before the start of the broadcast	3.54	SA
2.3 Informs the parents of the platforms to access the broadcast (e.g. through radio, via Facebook live).	3.15 3.46	A SA
3. Prepare/ready the materials learners need before listening to the audio lessons		
3.1 Direct the parents to refer to the textbook and provides the page number for quick reference	3.77	SA
3.2 Explains the instruction for the lesson to the parents through text message, chat, and/or call	3.77	SA
3.3 Instruct the parents to prepare the learning materials (e.g. self-learning modules, writing materials, textbooks) and gadgets needed for the lesson	3.54	SA
4. Recall the last week lesson		
4.1 Provides parents a set of questions to facilitate the review/recall	3.15	A
4.2 Provide the parents a copy of the recorded broadcast for review	3.46	SA
4.3 Follow-up the parents if they have conducted a review with their children	3.38	SA
Grand Mean	3.44	SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

Indicator 2, “*Constantly reminds the parents/guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast*”. Indicator 2.1 Sends a text or chat message to the parents with a mean score of 3.54 and verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Indicator 2.2 Call the parents before the start of the broadcast with mean score of 3.15 and verbal interpretation agree and indicator 2.3 Informs the parents of the platforms to access the broadcast such as through radio or via Facebook live with mean score 3.46 as Strongly Agree. The highest weighted mean by the teachers is to send messages to the parents because this is the easiest way to communicate with them. According to Bhamani, et al (2020) revealed that parents believed that through a schedule routine helps children to understand the importance of time, scheduling and doing assignments on a given timeline and help them shape their future work habits. Furthermore, by informing the parents regarding the schedule of broadcast it makes it easier for them to teach their children with the help of a radio teacher.

Indicator 3, “*Prepare/ready the materials of the learners needed before listening to the audio lessons*”. Indicator 3.1, directs the parents to refer to the textbook and provides the page number for quick reference with 3.77 and verbal interpretation of strongly Agree. In the indicator 3.2 Explains the instruction for the lesson to the parents through text message, chat, and/or call with 3.77 as strongly agree. In the 3.3 Instruct the parents to prepare the learning materials such as self-learning modules, writing materials, textbooks and gadgets needed for the lesson with 3.54 weighted mean strongly agree. The teachers request the parents to prepare the material of their children using the textbooks provided by the school. (Tety, 2016) findings revealed that teachers consider instructional materials as key to academic performance. In this regard, by preparing the materials the learner needs like textbooks, it will help the students to follow the instructions given by the audio teacher. The teachers direct the parents to refer to the textbook and provide the page number for quick reference by stating it in the Work Home learning plan every week (WHLP). It indicates the instruction for the lesson to the parents through text message or printed material.

Indicator 4, “*Recall last week's lesson*”. Indicator 4.2 got the highest weighted mean score 3.46 described as providing the parents a copy of the recorded broadcast for review. Indicator 4.3 Follow-up the parents if they have conducted a review with their children mean score 3.38. Both indicators 4.2 and 4.3 strongly agree. The lowest weighted mean is the indicator 4.1 Provides parents a set of questions to facilitate the review/recall with a mean score of 3.15 as Agree. (Davies, et al 2016) conclude that most students that have recorded lessons helped them understand the material and made studying more efficient. This is similar in the actual settings, when the pupil was not able to answer or parents could not pass the activity in time of retrieval, the teacher sends the copy of the recorded lesson/ broadcast for review through messenger. Teachers ask the parents' follow up in reviewing their child. However, few teachers answer that they did not provide the set of questions to the parents because most of the parents already know how to simply ask questions to review their child. It is also highlighted in the study of Lara & Saracostti (2019) that parental involvement can support learning activities at home through communication between family and school. This will make a strong formation of learning.

The mean score of teachers' collaborations on radio-based instruction during broadcast as shown in table 4, with the grand mean of 3.47 (SA) strongly agree.

In indicator 1, “*Check pupils' attendance during the broadcast.*” Indicator 1.1 encourage parents to send Facebook live comments with the school's name and section of their child with weighted mean 3.38. Indicator 1.2 Encourage parents to send pictures of their child to the teacher while tuned in on the broadcast through group chat with 3.46 weighted mean and Indicator 1.3 Encourage the parents to send a message while their child is tuned-in to the broadcast with 3.46. All sub-indicators got a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. It shows that during the broadcast the highest answers of the teachers belongs to sending messages of their child and encouraging their child to send comments or answers to the broadcast. (Yuvaraj, et al, 2017) conclude that attendance is an important matter since it is one of the ways to check the regularity of every student. Teachers will know the status of the child if he can accomplish the activity and understand the lesson in the time frame given with the cooperation of the Kindergarten parents.

Table 4 Mean Score of Teachers' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of During Broadcast

Indicator	Teacher	
	WM	Intp.
1. Check pupils' attendance during the broadcast		
1.1 Encourage parents to send Facebook live comment with the school name and section of their child	3.38	SA
1.2 Encourage parents to send pictures of their child to the teacher while tuned in on the broadcast through group chat	3.46	SA
1.3 Encourage the parents to send a message while their child is tuned-in to the broadcast (e.g. messenger, SMS, text message)	3.46	SA
2. Assist learners while tuned-in to the audio lesson;		
2.1 Encourage the parents to observe the child while tuned-in to the audio lesson	3.54	SA
2.2 Encourage the parent to send updates on their observation of their children	3.46	SA
2.3 Give parents clear instruction and explanation of the topic in the audio-lesson	3.38	SA

3. Perform the task given by the radio teacher	
3.1 Instruct the parents to direct their child to repeat the sounds after the radio broadcaster	3.38 SA
3.2 Encourage the parents to model the task given by the radio teacher	3.54 SA
3.3 Encourage the parents to use the textbook as reference/guide of the child	3.62 SA
Grand Mean	3.47 SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

In Indicator 2, “*Assist learners while tuned-in to the audio lesson.*” All the indicators have its verbal interpretation of Strongly agree. The Indicator 2.1 encourages the parents to observe the child while tuned-in to the audio lesson which has a weighted mean of 3.54 which is the highest rate in indicator 2. It shows the collaboration of parents to the teachers by assisting their child in the audio lesson. Followed by indicator 2.2 Encourage the parent to send updates on their observation of their children with 3.46 and indicator 2.3 Give parents clear instruction and explanation of the topic in the audio-lesson with 3.38. (Rahman, et al. 2019) findings in their study that in order to provide parents with ideas about children's learning activities, it is important to provide them the opportunity to observe activities. Through observation, parents will know in what particular areas is the weakness of their children and assist the learners while tune-in to the audio lessons.

The indicator 3, “*Perform the task given by the radio teacher*”. All the indicators are Strongly Agree. The statement that is mostly done by the teachers to the parents is the indicator 3.1. Encourage the parents to use the textbook as reference/guide of the child with 3.62 weighted mean. Followed by the indicator 3.2 Encourage the parents to model the task given by the radio teacher with 3.54 and indicator 3.1 Instruct the parents to direct their child to repeat the sounds after the radio broadcaster with 3.38. Data shows that teachers told the parents to use textbooks provided by SDO Biñan. Anora (2020) defined listening requires clear instructions and explanations in each activity for students to get a perfect understanding. When a learner understands the lesson, he can answer and follow the instructions of the radio teacher. Each of the pupils have its own materials to answer during the broadcast for them to perform the task needed weekly.

The mean score of teachers’ collaborations on radio-based instruction after broadcast as shown in table 5, with the grand mean of 3.46 (SA) strongly agree.

The indicator 1, “*Guide learners in accomplishing learning tasks/activity sheets*”. All the sub-indicators strongly agree. The 1.1 encouraging parents to send updates while the child is accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets with 3.62 weighted mean is the most answered by the teachers. Indicator 1.2 Clarify the instructions of the learning tasks to the parents with 3.54 and least is 1.1, remind the parents of the tasks indicated in the Weekly Home Learning Plan with 3.38. Baralt & Gomez (2017) says that Implementing task-based methodology during real-time is fundamentally different from face-to-face interaction. Teachers must manage both interaction and learner attention in an electronic platform that disperses learners’ attention more easily than traditional classrooms. Through the help of parents, they guide the learners in answering the activity sheets and textbooks. Parents ask questions to the teacher if the learners encounter difficulties in answering the activity sheets using fb group chat.

Indicator 2, “*Follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion encountered by pupils about the audio lessons*”. All the sub-indicators have a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. In the indicator 2.1 Gives a call to the parents or guardian to follow up clarifications with 3.46 weight mean, highest rate of the teachers. The indicator 2.3, Encourage the parents to send questions of learners about the audio-lessons through text message and/or chats with weighted mean of 3.38. Indicator 2.2 Conduct quarterly parent-teacher virtual conference to discuss learner’s questions about the audio lessons 3.31 weighted mean. The radio teacher entertains questions during the lesson and encourages everyone to answer in Facebook live comment. In regard to the quarterly meeting, it is done online via google meet platform but because of poverty, most parents cannot attend to this platform. That is why the announcement and questions are posted to Facebook group chat so everyone will be enlightened about the questions of one another and know what to do with their child when they encounter difficulties. On the other hand, (Kraft 2017) proved that messaging has also proved to be effective in boosting parent engagement and student achievement. Messaging is one of the basics in communicating with parents for the areas of clarification. Most teachers call the parents for other clarification instead of sending questions about the audio lessons. Many parents have no load to answer the teacher on Facebook. A call from a teacher is more accessible for them.

Table 5 Mean Score of Teachers' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of After Broadcast

Indicator	Teacher	
	WM	Intp.
1. Guide learners in accomplishing learning tasks/activity sheets		
1.1 Remind the parents of the tasks indicated in the Weekly Home Learning Plan	3.38	SA
1.2 Clarify the instructions of the learning tasks to the parents	3.54	SA
1.3 Encourage parents to send updates while the child is accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets	3.62	SA
2. Follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion encountered by pupils about the audio lessons		
2.1 Gives a call to the parents or guardian to follow up clarifications	3.31	SA
2.2 Conduct quarterly parent-teacher virtual conference to discuss learner's questions about the audio lessons	3.38	SA
2.3 Encourage the parents to send questions of learners about the audio-lessons through text message and/or chats	3.31	SA
3. Document the participation of learners and parents/guardians		
3.1 Explain to parents the documentation procedures (e.g. photo documentation, text messages, narrative reports)	3.46	SA
3.2 Monitor regularly parents for updates on the progress of the child in accomplishing the learning tasks	3.31	SA
3.3 Record pupil's attendance and submitted outputs regularly	3.38	SA
4. Submit the learning outputs of the learners during the scheduled retrieval		
4.1 Inform the parents of the schedule and procedures of submission of learner's outputs during retrieval	3.62	SA
4.2 Extend the time of submission of output for parents with difficulties and/or constraints (e.g. distant from school, working parents, unavailable parent/guardian)	3.54	SA
4.3 Remind/ follow-up and give updates to parents about the submission of learning outputs	3.62	SA
Grand Mean	3.46	SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

Indicator 3, *Documenting the participation of learners and parents/guardians.*” The whole sub-indicators have its verbal interpretation of strongly agree. In the indicator 3.1 Explain to parents the documentation procedures such as photo documentation, text messages, narrative reports with weighted mean 3.46. Followed by the indicator 3.3 Record pupil's attendance and submitted outputs regularly with 3.38 weighted mean and indicator 3.2 Monitor regularly parents for updates on the progress of the child in accomplishing the learning tasks. Data confirmed that teachers explained to parents the documentation procedure which got the highest weighted mean. Before the school year starts, the teachers give data privacy consent to each of the parents if they are willing to share the details and pictures of their child for school purposes only. 95% of the total population of kindergarten learners responds and gives their consent. In this regard, teachers explain the procedures and objectives in documenting the learner's output. The lowest weighted mean is monitoring the parents and sending updates on the progress of the child in accomplishing learning tasks because due to household chores, most parents cannot send updates of their child. Knauf (2020) suggests that the teachers created techniques primarily to gain time for documentation and to organize it in such a way that they can cope with the additional responsibilities it implies.

As per indicator 4, *“Submit the learning outputs of the learners during the scheduled retrieval.”* All strongly agree in verbal interpretation which shows that teachers collaborate with the parents. The indicator 4.1 informs the parents of the schedule and procedures of submission of learner's outputs during retrieval 3.62 and indicator 4.3 Remind or follow-up and give updates to parents about the submission of learning outputs with 3.62 mean score. The lowest indicator is 4.2. Extend the time of submission of output for parents with difficulties and/or constraints such as distance from school, working parents, unavailable parent/guardian with weighted mean of 3.54. Data shows that teachers did all the sub-indicators in collaborating with the parents in terms of retrieval

schedule. Teachers send text messages and group chat messages to the parents to inform the schedule of retrieval in school. According to Halimah & Andriyadi (2018) through a short message service (SMS)-gateway will help parents to gather information from Kindergarten teachers. The parents will be informed and will become updated in the submission of retrieval of their children.

Moreover, the kindergarten classes are divided into 2 groups. The first group will retrieve every Friday and the other group will retrieve every Saturday so that social distancing will be observed. Teachers also extended their time when some parents had constraints in distance in school and household chores especially to those parents who had more than three children.

The mean score of parents' collaborations on radio-based instruction before broadcast as shown in table 6, with the grand mean of 3.44 (SA) strongly agree.

The indicator 1, gives the weekly schedule of the broadcast. All sub indicators strongly agree and the highest rate is 3.54 which receives the link of the broadcast through Facebook chat. Followed by 3.53 which receives a printed/digital copy of the weekly schedule of broadcast from the teacher and the lowest indicator is 1.2 Informed about the coverage/topic of the audio lesson personally during retrieval with 3.41 weighted mean. Bordalba & Bochaca (2019) findings revealed that parents and teachers display more positive stances on the use of digital media like Facebook where the management team promotes the use of emails or online platforms for family- school communication. The implication of the use of an online platform to send the link of broadcast is easier for them to access the radio broadcast via Facebook live.

As per indicator 2, constantly remind the parents/guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast that all the sub indicators reached a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Indicator 2.1 is the highest weighted mean which is Receives and confirms a text or chat message from the teachers with 3.56 weighted mean. Indicator 2.2 Receives and answers a reminder call from the teacher before the start of the broadcast with weighted mean 3.43. Indicator 2.3 Informed about the platforms to access the broadcast through radio or via Facebook live with 3.42 weighted mean. Parents confirm a text from the teachers same with the answer of the teachers which states that they send messages to the parents. They also received a reminder call and informed the platform to access the broadcast. Myende & Nhlumayo (2020) suggest that when cooperating with schools, parents should examine the relevant concepts of parental involvement and evaluate the roles of parents from various scenarios. In this regard, parents know their responsibility and confirm messages from the teacher about the schedule of broadcast.

Table 6 Mean Score of Parents' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Before Broadcast

Indicator	Parent	
	WM	Intp.
1. Give weekly schedule of the broadcast		
1.1 Receives a printed/digital copy of the weekly schedule of broadcast from the teacher	3.53	SA
1.2 Informed about the coverage/topic of the audio lesson personally during retrieval	3.41	SA
1.3 Receives the link of the broadcast through Facebook chat.	3.54	SA
2. Constantly remind the parents/guardians regarding the schedule of the broadcast		
2.1 Receives and confirms a text or chat message from the teachers	3.56	SA
2.2 Receives and answers a reminder call from the teacher before the start of the broadcast	3.43	SA
2.3 Informed about the platforms to access the broadcast (e.g. through radio, via Facebook live).	3.42	SA
3. Prepare/ready the materials learners need before listening to the audio lessons		
3.1 Familiarize with lesson in advance from the textbook based on the page numbers given by the teacher	3.40	SA
3.2 Explains the instruction for the lesson to the child	3.47	SA
3.3 Prepares the learning materials (e.g. self- learning modules, writing materials, textbooks) and gadgets needed for the lesson	3.54	SA
4. Recall the last week lesson		

4.1 Ask my child set of questions provided by the teacher to facilitate review/recall	3.33 SA
4.2 Asks the teacher for a copy of the recorded broadcast for my child to review	3.28 SA
4.3 Give updates on what transcribed during the review to the teacher	3.40 SA
Grand Mean	3.44 SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

In indicator 3, “*Prepare/ready the materials learners need before listening to the audio lessons*”. All sub indicators are strongly agreed as verbal interpretation. The indicator 3.3 is the highest weighted mean which prepares the learning materials such as self-learning modules, writing materials, textbooks and gadgets needed for the lesson with a 3.54 mean. Followed by 3.2 Explains the instruction for the lesson to the child 3.47 and least is indicator 3.1 Familiarize with lesson in advance from the textbook based on the page numbers given by the teacher 3.40 weighted mean. The parents prepare the learning materials of their child before the broadcast which shows that the parents collaborated with the teachers wherein the teachers explain the instruction to the parents using the WHLP. Firmanto, Sumarsono & Nur (2020) Parents serve as tutors for their children at home under this learning paradigm, while the school produces learning materials with comprehensive methods and an organized schedule. Therefore, the parents encourage and help their children in being able to follow the audio lessons in radiobroadcasting.

The indicator 4, “*Recalls last week's lesson*”. All sub-indicators are strongly agreeing. Parents give updates to the teachers on what happened during the review phase with the highest weighted mean with 3.40. Followed by indicator 4.1 Ask my child a set of questions provided by the teacher to facilitate review/recall with 3.33 weighted mean and the lowest is indicator 4.2 Ask the teacher for a copy of the recorded broadcast for my child to review with 3.28. Data indicates that the parents share an update of their child while reviewing the past lesson. According to Solak (2016) Pre-task exercises like listening to audio lessons are focused on arousing interest before the main action among students. (International Literacy Association, 2019) Systematic teaching involves a review and repetition to achieve mastery and makes the new experience more apparent and easier to understand for students. Whereas the audio lesson is designed to arouse the student's interest and involvement. In order that the parents can give an update to the teacher, the examples given in the audio lessons are visible inside the house so that learners can follow the teacher easily.

Table 7 shows the mean score of parents' collaborations on radio-based instruction during broadcast with the grand mean of 3.40 (SA) strongly agree.

The indicator 1, “*Check pupils' attendance during the broadcast*”. All verbal interpretations strongly agree. Highest mean score is indicator 1.2 send pictures of my child to the teacher while tuned in on the broadcast through group chat with 3.34 mean score. Followed by indicator 1.1 Inform the teacher of my child's attendance during the broadcast through text message, chat or Facebook live comment with 3.33 weighted mean and the lowest indicator is 1.3 Send a message while their child is tuned-in to the broadcast thru messenger or SMS with 3.30 mean score. Data shows that during the broadcast, the parents are cooperating with the teachers and send pictures during the airing of the lessons. According to Sønsthagen (2020) in this time of pandemic and parents are the one who can monitor the learners, parents should share information regarding students' daily routine. In this regard, parents and teachers interact and achieve the same objective.

Table 7 Mean Score of Parents' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of During Broadcast

Indicator	Parent	
	WM	Intp.
1. Check pupils' attendance during the broadcast		
1.1 Inform the teacher of my child's attendance during the broadcast (e.g. through text message, chat, Facebook comments)	3.33	SA
1.2 Send pictures of my child to the teacher while tuned in on the broadcast through group chat	3.34	SA
1.3 Send a message while their child is tuned-in to the broadcast (e.g. messenger, text message)	3.30	SA
2. Assist learners while tuned-in to the audio lesson;		
2.1 Look after my child while listening to the audio lesson	3.36	SA
2.2 Instruct my child to do the task given by the radio teacher	3.49	SA
2.3 Explains the directions of the tasks given by the audio-teacher	3.51	SA
3. Perform the task given by the radio teacher		

3.1 Instruct the child to repeat the sounds after the radio broadcaster	3.43	SA
3.2 Demonstrate/model the task given by the radio teacher	3.35	SA
3.3 Direct my child to use the textbook as reference/guide for the topic	3.54	SA
Grand Mean	3.40	SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

Indicator 2, “*Assist learners while tuned-in to the audio lesson*”. All sub- indicators are strongly agreeing and the highest weighted mean is the indicator 2.3 which explains the directions of the tasks given by the audio-teacher with 3.51 weighted mean. Next is indicator 2.2 Instruct my child to do the task given by the radio teacher 3.49 mean score and lowest indicator is 2.1 Look after my child while listening to the audio lesson with 3.36. Data shows that parents strongly agreed that they explain the directions to their child and assist them during the broadcast. Aranas (2016) found out that teachers can customize lessons with interesting learning materials, engage students during instruction, and encourage them to repeat the lessons for independent practice on their own. Through this statement, parents may encourage the learners and guide them step-by-step since the learners are in the preschool level.

Indicator 3, “*Perform the task given by the radio teacher*”. All the indicators have the same verbal interpretation of strongly agree and the highest weighted mean is the sub indicator 3.3. Direct my child to use the textbook as reference/guide for the topic with 3.54 weighted mean. Followed by indicator 3.1 Instruct the child to repeat the sounds after the radio broadcaster with 3.43 weighted mean and the lowest indicator is 3.2 Demonstrate/model the task given by the radio teacher 3.35. Ose (2016) found out that by providing different sensory experiences, teachers can help their students learn and retain information. Similarly, Ivone & Renandya (2019) findings that using authentic materials can be made more comprehensible, giving learners the chance to read accompanied by written text while listening. However, in the study of Rogowsky, Calhoun, & Tallal (2016) showed that the using different modality in comprehension did not matter even if learners listen to an audiobook or read from a book or both listen and read simultaneously because learners received an equal amount of information. Juwariyah, Slamet & Kustiono (2019) conclude that parents should allow their children to express what they see and feel so that they can simply react to what they are given. Children can easily adopt the flow of the audio and visual instruction when they see and feel their parents' support. In this connection, parents' cooperation with their children's studies made the child boost their confidence and learning will become experiential.

Table 8 shows the mean score of parents’ collaborations on radio-based instruction after broadcast with the grand mean of 3.42 (SA) strongly agree. Each part of the indicators is Strongly agreeing.

In indicator 1, “*Guide learners in accomplishing learning tasks/activity sheets*” The highest weighted mean is indicator 1.2 which is Clarify the instructions of the learning tasks to my child 3.50 weighted mean. Followed by the 1.3 Send updates to the teachers while my child is accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets with 3.44 and the lowest is the indicator 1.1 Refer to the weekly home learning plan for the learning tasks/activity sheets to be accomplished by my child 3.35. Since, the new normal is the parent who will guide the learners in accomplishing the task, parents encounter problems in teaching their own child. Kuhn et. al. (2016) parents and teachers of young children must create successful partnerships. Teachers help and guide the parents to assist their child at home in accomplishing their task. Therefore, clarifying instructions to their child would enable parents and teachers to work together to anticipate, prevent, or solve children's behaviors.

Table 8 Mean Score of Parents’ Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction in terms of After Broadcast

Indicator	Parent	
	WM	Intp.
1. Guide learners in accomplishing learning tasks/activity sheets		
1.1 Refer to the weekly home learning plan for the learning tasks/activity sheets to be accomplished by my child	3.35	SA
1.2 Clarify the instructions of the learning tasks to my child	3.50	SA
1.3 Send updates to the teachers while my child is accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets	3.44	SA
2. Follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion		

2.1	encountered by pupils about the audio lessons Call the teachers to follow up clarifications encountered by my child	3.30	SA
2.2	Participate in the quarterly parent-teacher virtual conference to discuss questions about the audio lessons	3.31	SA
2.3	Send questions of learners about the audio- lessons through text message and/or chats	3.36	SA
3.	Document the participation of learners and parents/guardians		
3.1	Familiarize and acknowledge the documentation procedures (e.g. photo documentation, text messages)	3.37	SA
3.2	Send updates to teachers on the progress of my child in accomplishing the learning tasks	3.35	SA
3.3	Check the work/tasks accomplished by my child before submission	3.52	SA
4.	Submit the learning outputs of the learners during the scheduled retrieval		
4.1	Familiarize with the schedule and procedures of submission of my child's outputs during retrieval	3.52	SA
4.2	Inform the teacher about delayed submissions and difficulties / constraints during submission (e.g. distance from school, working parents, unavailable parent/guardian)	3.44	SA
4.3	Acknowledge reminders/ follow-up and give updates to the teachers about the submission of learning outputs	3.59	SA
Grand Mean		3.42	SA

4 - Strongly Agree (SA); 3 - Agree (A); 2 -Disagree (D); 1 -Strongly Disagree

Indicator 2, “*Follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion encountered by pupils about the audio lessons.*” Highest weighted mean is the indicator 2.3 which send questions of learners about the audio-lessons through text message and/or chats with weighted mean of 3.36. Next is the indicator 2.2 Participate in the quarterly parent-teacher virtual conference to discuss questions about and the lowest is the indicator 2.1 Call the teachers to follow up clarifications encountered by my child with 3.30 weighted mean. All the indicators got strongly agree as verbal interpretation. Calling the teachers for clarification is the least because since the lesson is in mother-tongue language, parents understand the lesson easily. Infact, every retrieval the parents can ask questions directly to the teacher regarding the clarifications and the most common type of communication that you don't need to wait for a call or meetings is by sending a text message or a personal chat to the teacher. Waterford (2018) parents and teachers should pay attention to one another and exchange ideas or inquiries. Parent-teacher conferences, phone conversations, and committee meetings are all examples of two-way communication. Using two-way communication, parents and teachers may build a positive parent relationship.

As per Indicator 3, “*Document the participation of learners and parents/guardians.*” Indicator 3.3 Check the work/tasks accomplished by my child before submission with 3.52 is the highest score. Followed by indicator 3.1 Familiarize and acknowledge the documentation procedures such as photo documentation and text messages with 3.37 weighted mean and the lowest indicator is 3.2 Send updates to teachers on the progress of my child in accomplishing the learning tasks 3.35 score. All the sub indicators strongly agree in verbal interpretation. In accomplishing the task given for the week, parents ask questions to the child before the learner answers the task to know if the learner understands the lesson. (Al-Batal, n.d.) describes that a post-listening practice is a follow-up to the listening activity which attempts to use the skills acquired by listening to improve other skills, such as speaking or writing. In addition, Kuhn, M., Marvin, C. A., & Knoche, L. L. (2016) encourages parents to keep track of their children's progress and track their progress toward their goals. Discuss necessary adjustments in interactions and/or learning opportunities using data. As needed, adjust to new developmental demands and learning opportunities. However, Higgins & Cherrington (2017) highlighted the significance of making learning visible by accomplishing the tasks, rather than simply providing photographic evidence.

The last indicator “*Submit the learning outputs of the learners during the scheduled retrieval*”. The indicator 4.3 Acknowledge reminders/ follow-up and give updates from teachers about the submission of learning outputs 3.59 got the highest weighted mean. Followed by indicator 4.1 Familiarize with the schedule and procedures of

submission of my child's outputs during retrieval 3.52 and indicator 4.2 Inform the teacher about delayed submissions and difficulties/constraints during submission such as distance from school, working parents, unavailable parent/guardian with 3.44 mean score. According to Pact (2016) Monitoring is the practice of gathering and reviewing information systematically to monitor the success of the curriculum in meeting objectives and observe improvements in conflict or surroundings. By submitting the learning output of the child in the schedule of retrieval, teachers may give updates to the parents regarding the accomplishment done by the learners.

Recapitulation

Table 9 Summary Table on Mean Score on Parents' and Teachers' Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction

Indicator	Parent		Teacher	
	Grand Mean	Interpretation	Grand Mean	Interpretation
Before Broadcast	3.44	SA	3.44	SA
During Broadcast	3.40	SA	3.47	SA
After Broadcast	3.42	SA	3.46	SA

Indicator 3 After the broadcast, parents weighted mean was 3.42 while teachers are 3.46 grand mean. It showed that all verbal interpretation is strongly agree. Both parents and teachers have the least score in calling a parent or guardian to follow up clarification.

Result of Hypothesis Testing

Table 9 shows the summary of tables on mean score on parents and teachers' collaboration on radio-based instruction before, during and after broadcast.

Indicator 1, before the broadcast parents and teachers had the same grand mean which is 3.44 with the same verbal interpretation strongly agree. In some parts of the teachers' rating with the interpretation of Agree in providing a printed copy and calling the parents before the start of the program. Overall, both parents and teachers followed the same procedure before the broadcast.

Table 10 Results of ANOVA on the Mean Difference

Indicator	Critical Values	Computed Value	Interpretation	Decision
Before Broadcast	3.88	0.004	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	3.88	0.44	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	3.88	0.053	significant	Ho Not Accepted

Level of Significance: 0.05

Indicator 2, during the broadcast, parents have 3.40 grand mean while the teacher represents a grand mean of 3.47. Both are with verbal interpretation of Strongly agree. Sending a message to the teacher while tuned in to the broadcast is the least weighted mean to the parents because most of them have only one cellular phone in the family. It is hard for them to send messages during the broadcast while the lowest score for the teacher is encouraging parents to send Facebook live comments with the school's name and section of their child because parents already know what to do during the broadcast.

Table 10 shows the result of ANOVA on the mean difference of before, during and after broadcast. The computed F-value 0.004 for before the broadcast is lower than the critical value 3.88. It indicates there is no significant verbal interpretation which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference on how parents and teachers collaborate before broadcast. Smith et al (2016) explained that parents manage several responsibilities traditionally assigned to the teacher. Such as implementing instruction, preparing learning materials, giving updates on what transcribed radio-teachers, and acting as their children's at-home teachers.

The computed f-value 0.44 for during the broadcast is lower than the critical value 3.88. Its verbal interpretation is not significant therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. It means that there is no significant difference on how the parents and teachers collaborate in Radiobroadcasting during the broadcast. Vourinen (2018) describes parents and teachers who appear to have the same values, norms, and ideas about practice and children's needs. The teachers encourage the parents to model the task given by the radio teacher and the parents demonstrate the task to the learners.

The computed f-value 0.053 for after the broadcast is lower 3.88 critical value. It implies that there is no significant difference on how the parents and teachers collaborate after the broadcast. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Goshen (2020) pointed out the critical role of home and family environment in determining children's kindergarten success. An active and positive collaboration between teachers and parents in kindergarten is crucial on both sides. Developing close relationships between parents and teachers based on attitudes and feelings of both parties is highly important. In addition, Wood, et al (2020) study shows the potential of involving parents in their children's educational interventions as a valuable addition to or alternative to traditional child-directed intervention programs to increase positive outcomes and enhance parental efficacy. Both parents and teachers mean scores after the broadcast scored low to indicator 2 in which the teachers should follow up learners for clarification and areas of confusion encountered by the pupil.

Table 11 revealed the significant relationship between teachers' profile and collaboration on radio-based instruction.

Relative to age of the teachers, the computed r-value -0.46 for before the broadcast showed low positive / negative correlation; -0.26 during the broadcast negligible correlation while -0.15 after the broadcast negligible correlation. It showed that there is no significant relationship between teachers' age and collaboration in radio-based instruction before, during and after the broadcast. Teachers are using the institutional standardized implementation in RBI during Before the broadcast. Teachers give a weekly schedule of the broadcast, constantly remind the parents regarding the schedule of the broadcast, prepare the materials of the learners needed before listening activities and review the last week's lesson. Based on the data, teachers check pupils' attendance during the broadcast, assist learners while tuned- in to the audio lessons, and perform the task given by the radio teacher. After the broadcast, guide learners in accomplishing learning tasks/activity sheets, follow-up learners for clarifications and areas of confusion encountered by pupils about the audio lessons, document the participation of learners and parents/guardians and Submit the learning outputs of the learners during the scheduled retrieval. Regardless of their age, Anthony et al (2019) teachers can adopt the new situation by helping each other to succeed and adopt the new modality. Principal, coaches, department chairs, and curriculum coordinators may help to support teachers' learning and through this, teachers may share to the parents the needs to be considered to adopt the new modality. However, the study of Fauzi (2020) teachers understand the context of distance learning, but there are several implementation issues, such as the availability of radio, network and internet usage for updates, and collaboration with parents.

Table 11 Significant Relationship Between Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction and Teachers' Profile

	Computed R-value	Intp.	Ho Remarks	Decision
Age				
Before Broadcast	-0.46	Low Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	-0.26	Negligible Correlation	Not Significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	-0.15	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
Sex				
Before Broadcast		Relationship cannot be determined		
During Broadcast		Relationship cannot be determined		
After Broadcast		Relationship cannot be determined		
Educational Attainment				
Before Broadcast	0.23	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	0.04	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	0.39	Low Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
Length of Service				
Before Broadcast	-0.37	Low Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	-0.24	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	0.05	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted

In terms of sex, the teachers are all female so that the relationship cannot be determined. There is no relationship between sex and the collaboration of the radio- based instruction. They may have differences in mean score, but they belong to the same sex. The female teachers have a mother instinct and know how to collaborate with parents of any gender. Gülçiçek, (2017) found that male teachers in kindergarten have an inability to deal with

children's self-care. Furthermore, they were seen to be incapable of communicating with females, and because male teachers are unable to be mothers, they were seen as a disadvantage by parents. However, male teachers had more influence over children and that male teacher not being mothers makes an advantage to them. Therefore, both male and female teachers can improve their chances in areas where they are weak.

The educational attainment of the teachers the computed r-value 0.23 for before and during the broadcast 0.04 were both negligible correlation and 0.39 after with verbal interpretation of low positive correlation/ negative correlation. In regard to educational attainment, teachers have the same procedure and in the same institution in collaborating with the parents before, during and after the broadcast.

When a teacher has completed the four-year course that provides the groundwork for being a competent primary school teacher, they are qualified in the teaching field. Even the radio-based instruction is newly implemented, the teachers undergo training and workshops. Bolivecova et al (2021) concludes that enhancing the professional training of teachers is currently a requirement not only the required level of professional knowledge, but also psychological training, self-management and orientation to the required activities. Using the knowledge in training and workshops, teachers enhance their capabilities and can share their knowledge to the parents who are in direct contact with the learners. It showed that there is no significant relationship between teachers' educational attainment and collaboration in radio-based instruction before, during and after the broadcast.

In relation to length of service the critical value of before is -0.37 low negative correlation which means that there is no significant relationship between the length of service and the collaboration of teachers in Radio-based Instruction. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. While the computed R-value -0.24 for during broadcast and 0.05 after broadcast denotes negligible correlation; both values connote that there is no significant relationship between the length of service of teachers and collaboration of teachers in radio-based instruction. The null hypothesis is accepted. It means that regardless of the length of service of the teacher, they are experienced, and they know how to handle parents and how to collaborate with the parents in radio-based instruction. According to the findings of Meehan & Meehan (2017), teachers have a difficulty in terms of their confidence in establishing interactions with parents, as well as their feelings of being competent but inexperienced. Metsala & Specht (2018) findings that It is critical to get new teachers to the point where they believe they are capable and are emotionally prepared to deal with the stresses of the learners. However, Goshen (2020) new teachers, who have limited experience regarding ways to encourage parental involvement will refer to the practices such as reaching out to parents and encouraging their involvement. Regardless of the teacher being a novice or experienced, Castillon & Bonotan (2018) recommend that a seminar/training for teachers on facilitating strong home-school partnership. Therefore, even if teachers are inexperienced in Radio-based instruction, they may be equipped with the needed knowledge, values and skills for this important noble task in collaborating with parents.

The relationship between collaboration on radio-based instruction and parents' profile as shown in table 12. The computed r-value in age of parents before the broadcast is 0.03, during -0.06 and -0.05 after the broadcast with the verbal interpretation negligible correlation. It means that there is no significant relationship between the age of parents and collaboration on radio-based instruction. The null hypothesis is accepted.

The study of Grigoryeva (2017) showed that parents aged 40 years old and above and with more than two children failed to collaborate with the teachers. It is since parent, cannot handle more than two children at home specially when they have household chores, However, according to Raising Children (2018) regardless of parents' age, parents can model positive thinking in working and talking with the teacher. Therefore, parents may ask simple problem-solution steps to teachers for some difficulties of their child. Parents are given constant follow up, and reminders so that parents of any age can follow the procedures. When parents are given clear instructions and directions, as well as assistance by teachers, they can serve as role models for their children at home in the radio-based instruction.

Table 12 Significant Relationship Between Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction and Parents' Profile

	Computed r-value	Interpretation	Ho Remarks	Decision
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Age				
Before Broadcast	0.03	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	-0.06	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	-0.05	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
Sex				
Before Broadcast	0.007	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	0.10	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	0.09	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment				
Before Broadcast	0.14	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	0.17	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	0.15	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
Employment Status				
Before Broadcast	-0.004	No Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
During Broadcast	0.0016	No Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted
After Broadcast	-0.03	Negligible Correlation	Not significant	Ho Accepted

In terms of sex, the computed R-value 0.007 before the broadcast, 0.10 for during broadcast and 0.09 after the broadcast with negligible correlation as verbal interpretation. Indicating that there is no significant relationship of sex of parents and collaboration on radio-based instruction. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. According to Mora-Ruano, et al (2018) women collaborate more than men when they are the same gender in two or three forms of collaboration such as synchronization, co-construction and interest. The result is with negligible correlation in the actual study because there were more mothers than fathers that are active in schoolwork and hands-on to their child. Furthermore, Lau & Powers (2018) conclude that parents in any gender should engage in their children's learning at home and at school, especially during the first year of primary school.

The computed R-value of educational attainment of the parents are before 0.14, during 0.17 and after the broadcast is 0.15. Its verbal interpretation is negligible correlation. There is no significant difference between the educational attainment of the parents and the collaboration in radio-based instruction. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted. Teachers and parents can build healthy, collaborative connections by engaging in respectful forms of communication regardless of the educational background of parents. (Thorson, 2018) Parents are more likely to become more forceful in their child's development because they desire to teach them more than they learned in their own years. They are respective, more aggressive and cooperative in school to help their children in their studies.

In terms of parents' employment status, the computed R-value -0.004 for before, 0.0016 for during with verbal interpretation of no correlation. Indicating there is no significant relationship of employment status of parents and collaboration in radio-instruction. The null hypothesis is accepted. The computed R-value -0.03 for after broadcast with negligible correlation. There is no significant relationship between the parents' employment status and how they collaborate in the radio-based instruction. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Lau & Ng (2019) parents' unemployment relates to a negative impact on children's hope in academic progress. Since education in the Philippines is free for all, regardless of parent's employment status, they collaborate with the teachers and are more focused on their child school's progress.

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter sum up the foregoing chapters, enumerates the finding, states the conclusion and recommendation derived from the study.

The main thrust of the study is to determine the Radio-based instruction for Kindergarten: A Parent-Teacher Collaboration Activity in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langka, Biñan City, Laguna.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Teacher
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 - 1.1.3. Educational Attainment
 - 1.1.4. Length of Service
 - 1.2. Parent
 - 1.2.1. Age
 - 1.2.2. Sex
 - 1.2.3. Educational Attainment

- 1.2.4. Employment Status
2. How do parents and teachers collaborate in radio-based instruction in terms of?
 - 2.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 2.2. During the Broadcast
 - 2.3. After the Broadcast
3. What radio-based instruction Script in Mother-Tongue for Kindergarten may be developed?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference on how parents' and teachers' collaboration in Radio-Based Instruction in terms of:
 - 1.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 1.2. During the Broadcast
 - 1.3. After the Broadcast
2. There is no significant relationship between respondents' profile and how they collaborate in Radio-Based Instruction in terms of:
 - 2.1. Before the Broadcast
 - 2.2. During the Broadcast
 - 2.3. After the Broadcast

The study utilized descriptive research design and involved two hundred twenty-eight (228) parents and thirteen (13) teachers in Kindergarten as respondents in Southville 5A Elementary School-Langkiwa. The questionnaire is a teacher-made questionnaire that is used to gather the data. The data were tallied, analyzed and interpreted using (1) frequency and percentage of distribution, (2) weighted mean, (3) one-way ANOVA; (4) Pearson r Coefficient of Correlation.

Summary of Findings

The following derived salient findings as follows:

I. Respondents Profile

- A. Teachers.** Majority of the teachers are aged from 21-30 with 61.54%. All of the teachers were female. Most of the teachers were bachelor's degree with 61.54%. Majority of the teachers were from 4-9 years of service in teaching with 61.54%.
- B. Parents.** Majority of the parents were 21-30 years old with 43.42%. Most of them were female with 81.14%. The educational attainment showed that

72.37% of parents were high school graduates. Most of the parents were unemployed with 71.49%.

II. Collaboration in Radio-based instruction

A. Teachers

The grand mean score of teacher's collaborations on Radio-based instruction before the broadcast is 3.44

Strongly agree. According to the teachers before the broadcast, directing the parents to refer to the textbook and providing a page number for quick reference and explaining the instruction to parents through text message, chat or call with 3.77 weighted mean is an important collaboration with the parents before the broadcast.

During broadcast, the grand mean score of teachers' collaborations on radio-based instruction is 3.44 Strongly agree. Based on the responses, while performing the task given by the radio-teacher, encouraging parents to use the textbook as reference/guide of the child is significant in working together with the parents.

After the broadcast, the grand mean score of teachers' collaborations on radio-based instruction is 3.46 Strongly agree. Teachers confirmed that encouraging the parents to send updates while the child is accomplishing the learning tasks/activity sheets, informing the parents of the schedule and procedures of submission of learner's outputs and remind/follow-up and give updates to parents about the submission of learning outputs are important activities to have a successful partnership with parents in radio-based instruction.

B. Parents

The grand mean score of parents' collaborations on radio-based instruction in terms of before broadcast is 3.44 strongly agree. Parents noted that receiving and confirming text messages from teachers is one of the most important collaborations with the teachers.

During the broadcast, the grand mean score of parent's collaborations on radio-based instruction is 3.40 strongly agree. It shows that during the broadcast, parents direct the child to use the textbooks as reference guides for the topic and explain the directions of the task given by the audio-teacher.

The grand mean score of parents in collaboration on radio-based instruction after broadcasting is 3.42 strongly agree. Parents identify that submitting the learning output of the learners during the scheduled retrieval by acknowledging the reminders and giving updates to the teachers are the activities that are important in collaborating with the teachers.

III. Results of Hypothesis Testing of Significant Relationship

A. Teachers

a. Teachers' Age and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction.

Before the broadcast, teachers' age showed low positive/negative correlation with computed r-value-0.46. During broadcast, -0.26 with verbal

interpretation negligible correlation and -0.15 for after the broadcast with negligible correlation.

b. Teachers' Sex and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction. The relationship of sex of the teachers and collaboration in Radio-based instruction before, during and after cannot be determined.

c. Teachers' Educational attainment and Collaboration on Radio- Based Instruction. The evaluation showed that before the broadcast there is 0.23 negligible correlation: 0.04 during broadcast with negligible correlation verbal interpretation and 0.39 after broadcasting low positive correlation/negative correlation.

d. Teachers' length of service and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction. Data revealed a low positive correlation/ negative correlation with 0.37 before the broadcast; -0.24 negligible correlation during broadcast and 0.05 negligible correlation after broadcast.

B. Parents

a. Parents' Age and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction. Over all the test of significance relationship between the collaboration on the radio-based instruction and parents profile in terms of sex, age, educational attainment and employment status were all not significant and the null hypothesis is accepted.

b. Parents' Sex and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction. The computed R-value 0.007 before the broadcast, 0.10 during broadcast and 0.09 after the broadcast with negligible correlation as verbal interpretation.

c. Parents' Educational Attainment and Collaboration on Radio- Based Instruction. The computed R-value of educational attainment of the parents before 0.14, during 0.17 and after the broadcast is 0.15 showed negligible correlation between parents' educational attainment and collaboration on radio-based instruction.

d. Parents' Employment Status and Collaboration on Radio-Based Instruction. Data revealed no correlation between parents' employment status and collaboration in radio-based instruction as reflected in computed R-value -0.004 before, 0.0016 during, while -0.03 after broadcast with negligible correlation.

Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the parents and teachers' profile and the collaboration in radio-based instruction before, during and after the broadcast.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusion are drawn.

1. Profile of respondents

Teachers. All the teachers in kindergarten are female, indicating that they are more suitable in child formation because they have motherly instincts. They are all qualified as kindergarten teachers and five (5) of them continue to pursue their profession.

Parents. Majority of the parents are unemployed, as a result they supervise their child during, before and after the broadcast and monitor their child's activities. Parents follow the procedure in doing the radio- based instruction. They participate and collaborate in radio-based instruction.

2. Collaboration in Radio-based instruction

Teachers. Teachers establish an open communication with parents in different ways to guide the learners in radio-based instruction and to promote students' success in school.

Parents. Parents follow the procedure in doing the radio-based instruction. They participate and collaborate with the teachers by giving feedback and following the schedule of broadcast and retrieval. Some parents share that they are doing their part to guide and demonstrate to their children the lesson to help their learners in this time of pandemic.

3. Test of significant relationship

Teachers' profile and Collaboration in Radio-based Instruction. Teachers' age, sex, educational attainment and length of service are not related to collaboration in Radio-based Instruction before, during and after the broadcast.

Parents' profile and Collaboration in Radio-based instruction. The parents' age, sex, educational attainment, and employment status did not affect the collaboration to teachers in radio-based instruction before, during and after the broadcast. In every procedure during, before and after the broadcast parents are making a way to make the education of their child continue.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are hereby offered.

The Local Government

1. Provide radio to the community who had no cellphone or television in which the learner can continue their studies by using radio-instruction.
2. The Barangay community area may put megaphones in every post and aired the lesson for the learners within the community and benefited

those who had no access to radio lessons. Through this, learners can answer to the textbook or modules even if their parents are not at home.

School Administrator

1. Utilize the findings of this study for further organization and planning programs especially in kindergarten to enhance the reading skills especially in phonemic awareness.
2. Organize a free webinar/ workshop for parents on how to model or demonstrate the lessons in Radio-based instruction.
3. Determine the other possible teacher-parent issues in radio-based instruction behind the collaboration.
4. Establish a parent advisory board to provide suggested opportunities for parent involvement, education, and open communication.
5. Encourage parents to join in Parents and Teacher conferences
6. Provide a suggestion box for the improvement of Radio-instruction.

Teachers

1. Communicate to the parents who have reading disabilities and make an intervention for those pupils.
2. Design and implement strategies in teaching sounds through audio lessons,
3. Provide to some parents a copy of review before the broadcast especially to those parents who did not know how to facilitate the review phase.
4. Upgrade educational qualification by attending workshops for radio- instruction.
5. Support and collaborate with other stakeholders for the improvement of audio lessons.
6. Continue to monitor the progress of students and keep the parents informed about the school activities and ensure that learners have ways to learn outside the classroom.

Parents

1. Continue a strong partnership with the teachers in the formation or development of the children.
2. Model and encourage the child to repeat the sounds of what the radio teacher is saying.
3. Attend instructional workshops on early literacy and social development that may affects children's academic success.

Pupils

1. Encouraged to listen to the radio teacher to answer the task given.
2. Motivate to study even in this time of pandemic because education must continue.
3. Communicate to their parents for areas of confusion.

Future Researchers. Conduct a similar study on radio-based instruction focused on the problems encountered by students, parents and teachers and strategies to make the lessons in radio be more meaningful and livelier. In addition, the collaboration of other school stakeholders such as school staff, administrator can also be a subject to the similar study.

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